

Deliverable D6.2.

Pilot (ES) Technical report and achieved results (1|2)

Deliverable report

Deliverable No.	D6.2	Work Package No.	WP6	Task/s No.	Task 6.2
Work Package Title	PILOT SCENARIOS FOR QUARRYING OPERATIONS MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT				
Linked Task/s Title	Pilot implementation at CEMEX'S quarry-Valdilecha				
Status	Final	(Draft/Draft Final/Final)			
Dissemination level	PU	(PU-Public, RE-Restricted, CO-Confidential)			
Due date deliverable	2023-11-30	Submission date	2023-11-29		
Deliverable version	DEQ_D6.2_CEMEX_V1.0_20231129				

Document Contributors

Deliverable responsible	CEMEX	
Contributors	Organisation	
Patricia Carrión	CEMEX	
César Rocamora	CEMEX	
Jose Ramón Doheijo	CEMEX	
Ana Filipa Santos	CEMEX	
Pablo Segarra	UPM-M	
José A. Sanchidrián	UPM-M	
Reviewers	Organisation	
Lorena Viladés	ANEFA	
Paulo Romero	ANEFA	
Violeta Vázquez	ZABALA	

Document History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	2023-11-29	Final version

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the author's view. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the authors. The European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (**WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers**) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analyzing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analyzed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow **a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities**. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

To ensure a successful implementation of the developed technologies in the pilot sites, social risks identified in WP7 for each pilot have been carefully considered. WP6 also includes the assessment and monitoring of relevant KPIs, which will help reduce the risk of work accidents and minimize the environmental impact.

Table of contents

Deliverable report	3
Document Contributors	3
Document History	3
Disclaimer	4
Table of contents	5
List of Abbreviations	6
1 Pilot overview	7
2 Implementation of technologies	8
2.1 Selection and development of innovative aggregates processing techniques (WP2)	8
2.1.1 Advanced rock mass characterisation (Task 2.1.)	8
2.1.2 Adaptive blast design and novel explosives and blasting products and systems (Task 2.2.)	13
2.1.3 Blast output control: fragmentation, rock damage, muckpile properties and Innovative vibration measurement tools (Task 2.3.)	16
2.1.4 Drill-to-mill concept implementation (T2.4/WP6)	17
2.1.5 Productive and energy efficient drilling of hard rocks (Task 2.5.)	21
2.2 Identification of data inputs from cyber & physical quarrying system and development of sensors, automation and process control (WP3)	23
2.2.1 Monitoring sensors and analysing tools for Mobile Machinery (Task 3.3.)	23
2.3 Development of an integrated IoT/BIM/AI platform for smart quarrying (WP4)	24
2.3.1 ICT platform design and implementation (Task 4.2)	24
2.3.2 Data warehouse-AI (Task 4.3.)	24
2.3.3 BIM integration (Task 4.4.)	37
3 Conclusions	41
4 References	42
List of Figures	43
List of Tables	45

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite Systems
MWD	Measurement-While-Drilling
QA/QC	Quality Assurance/ Quality Control
ROM	Run-of-mine
RTK	Real Time Kinematics
SVM	Support Vector Machine
DEQ	DigiEcoQuarry
WP	Work Package

1 Pilot overview

The Valdilecha quarry is at the forefront of implementing Key Technology Area KTA1, focusing on enhanced extraction, rock mass characterization, and control. The quarry's primary project interest lies in studying and managing fines production from blasting, aiming to increase the yield of high-value final fractions while minimizing lower-value fractions. Various parameters will be measured, including structural rock conditions, lithology changes, geometrical characteristics of blasts, explosive mass, and timing sequence. The quarry will also focus on muckpile characterization, vibrations in the near-field for rock damage evaluation, and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for digging. The DigiEcoQuarry approach involves linking KPIs throughout the Mine-to-Mill process to reduce the ratio of unsuitable material for aggregate production, particularly fines.

Currently the quarry is developed across two areas: North (near the offices) and Northeast (see Figure 1). This last area has been mined in three benches (1,2 and 3) with different orientation (North, East, North-East and North-West).

Moreover, the Valdilecha quarry has seamlessly incorporated cross-cutting technologies from the project, including Building Information Modelling (BIM), ICT platform, and a cutting-edge IoT/BIM/AI platform. Leveraging the power of artificial intelligence algorithms, these technologies contribute to a comprehensive and integrated approach. BIM facilitates precise modelling of the quarry's structural elements, ICT enhances communication and data transfer efficiency, while the IoT/BIM/AI platform synergistically combines data from various sources for advanced analytics. The implementation of these technologies not only enhances the overall operational efficiency but also positions Valdilecha as a forward-thinking leader in the intersection of mining, technology, and artificial intelligence within the DigiEcoQuarry project.

2 Implementation of technologies

In Valdilecha, it has emerged as a trailblazer in the implementation of the advanced KTA 1 system, aimed at applying techniques for the characterization of the rock mass with the primary goal of refining drilling and blasting operations. This strategic approach seeks to optimize not only the overall efficiency of mining activities but also enhance the accuracy of drilling, a critical aspect for resource maximization and safety in project development. This report will closely examine the results achieved in Valdilecha, highlighting also in deploying cross-cutting technologies across all pilot sites of the project, thereby contributing to ongoing advancement and excellence in the quarry industry.

2.1 Selection and development of innovative aggregates processing techniques (WP2)

2.1.1 Advanced rock mass characterisation (Task 2.1.)

Manual and automatic characterization techniques have been adapted to the quarry conditions and applied to assess rock mass characteristics of 15 blasts made in Valdilecha quarry in the period January-July 2023. The first group of techniques comprises manual analysis of 3D models of the highwall face of the blasts, and of in-hole videos of the rock walls obtained with an endoscope. A detailed description of these two techniques is given in “D2.1-Advanced rock mass characterization techniques (I)” and it will be updated in “D2.11-Advanced rock mass characterization techniques (I)”.

Measurement-while-drilling technology has been employed to record the response of the drill rig to rock mass conditions, providing an automatic assessment of the rock classes (i.e., lithologies and discontinuities) that affect the performance of the drill rig. In-hole videos are used for MWD calibration purposes.

Mobile coverage in the Northeast side of the pit is very limited, preventing to make differential corrections in the raw coordinates provided e.g., by the drone, hence involving large errors (in the order of 5 m) which prevents – among other – accurate alignment of pre and post blast flight models. To correct this, MAXAM has deployed a local WIFI network composed by a system of permanent antennas that allows connectivity between them outside the pit, and a mobile one that is placed in the working area in line of sight of the fixed antenna. The mobile antenna collects the signal transmitted by the fixed antenna and provides WIFI coverage around it in a range of 400 m, enabling the connection to this local WIFI network of the drone or of MAXAM’s digital tools for a real time QA/QC before, during and after blasting. This allows a Real Time Kinematics (RTK) positioning to correct errors from Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS). Figure 6 (graphs a and b) shows a sketch of the network implementation, where a set of fixed and mobile antennas will allow to bring internet connection to the operation. Figure 1 shows images of the onsite installation of the fixed, to the left (internet receptor) and centre (Master antenna) and mobile (to the right) antennas.

Figure 1. Images of the antennas system installed: left – WIFI receptor, centre – master antenna, right – mobile antenna.

2.1.1.1 Manual characterization techniques

UPM-M has surveyed highwall faces of the block before the blasts with a drone Matrix 300 RTK Universal Edition with a Zenmuse P1 photogrammetric sensor manufactured by DJI. The flights were done manually as close as possible to the face of the block controlling the camera pitch manually to ensure that it is perpendicular to the face as much as possible and taking the photos manually by the operator. The resulting 3D models were analysed with the JMX Analyst Module (version 4.8) to map discontinuities. First, sub-horizontal discontinuities are marked based on their appearance in the bench face; the most apparent discontinuities are marked first, and then a more detailed inspection is made searching for less apparent sub-horizontal discontinuities. The highwall face is next inspected looking for sub-vertical discontinuities. If the trace of any of these discontinuities is not continuous, no assumption about the non-visible parts is made. As an example, the time spent to fully map a bench face of 13 m height and 50 m long is about 1 hour and 30 minutes. Figure 2 shows the 3D model of the blast 230612 made in bench 3 in the Northeast side of the pit and the discontinuities mapped.

Figure 2. 3D model of blast 230612 and mapped discontinuities (green and red horizontal axes define the North and East directions).

The outputs of this analysis are the orientation and length of each discontinuity, the spacing between discontinuities, and the areal fracture density P_{21} (i.e., fracture length over the investigated area). These data will be reported, for 15 blasts monitored, in D2.11 due to January 2024 and they will be used to build a discrete fracture network model for each blast and assess then the IBSD. They will be also used to quantify the effects of discontinuities and lithologies in fragmentation, rock pull and toe breakage.

Optical televiewer is considered the “golden standard” for borehole logging, providing an oriented 3D virtual core of the rock. It however requires at least two operators, and it is time consuming. On the opposite site endoscope cameras allow a massive logging of most of the boreholes of the blast by only one operator at the cost that the orientation of discontinuities and lithologies is unknown. UPM-M has developed a procedure for borehole logging with an endoscope camera manufactured by Forthaus Tech. The camera is 23 mm in diameter, and it is connected to the recording box by a 20 m pushing cable. An in-house plastic centralizer fixed to a metallic bar of about 1 m length has been developed to centralize the camera in the blasthole and ensure a good visualization of the borehole walls. The endoscope records a colour video of the internal walls of the blastholes with a resolution of 752x582 pixels; the camera's depth down the hole measured with a resolution of 10 cm is shown in the top part of the video. A comparison with measurements in eight holes with an optical televiewer shows that the endoscope resolution is enough to identify discontinuities and lithologies (including the amount of clay) crossed by the holes and to assess their position.

More than 4 km of rock from 332 boreholes in 15 blasts have been inspected. A library of six discontinuity types and seven lithologies has been built for a systematic analysis of the videos (see deliverables D2.1 and D2.11 for more details). For each hole, the rock classes with low and high confidence recognition levels are given as function of depth. The natural fragmentation of the rock is low with a discontinuity frequency (considering discontinuities recognised at low and high confidence levels) up to 0.281 m^{-1} . Among discontinuities, cavities/faults and weakness areas have a large effect on the

explosive mass charged into the hole and this data has been used in the blasts charged with RIOFLEX to anticipate the presence of cavities/faults and weakness, where the explosives densities could be high.

Measurements from the in-hole videos are used to build block models as the one in Figure 3, in which massive limestone with low amount of clay (magenta-coloured zones) and brecciated limestone (green coloured zones) are the predominant lithologies. The natural fines from the blast that are relevant to estimate the fines produced in blasting can be assessed, assigning an amount of clay of 0, 25, 50 and 75 % for lithologies with null, low, medium and high amount of clay, respectively. These are in the range 24-37 % for blasts made in bench 3 in the Northeast side of the pit, while they are lower (1-25 %) for blasts made in bench 1 of the North side of the quarry.

Figure 3. Block model of bench 3 in the Northeast part of the pit; the colors correspond to different lithologies: massive limestone with no clay (blue); massive limestone with low amount of clay (magenta); massive limestone with medium amount of clay (red); brecciated limestone with low amount of clay (green); brecciated limestone with medium amount of clay (yellow), brecciated limestone with high amount of clay (grey) and clay (brown).

As collateral work not included in the GA and due to long time spent for the analysis of the endoscope (two to three days depending on the holes inspected and their length), an automatic detection of lithologies from the endoscope videos has been attempted. A script in MATLAB environment has been developed to extract the images of the videos, read the corresponding depths from the digits in the upper left corner and extracts colour properties as red, green, blue pixel intensities and the texture of the images. These data are considered as inputs into a Machine learning model to classify the rock into three classes, namely class 0 with limited/low clay content, class 1 with medium clay content and class 2 with high clay content. The resulting confusion matrix from a Support Vector Machine (SVM) Quadratic method from the testing set is shown in Figure 4. The overall accuracy is 92 %, being the best recognition for class 0.

Figure 4. SVM confusion matrix for lithology classification from footage extracted from endoscope videos.

2.1.1.2 Automatic characterization techniques

Measurement-while-drilling allows an automatic assessment of lithologies and discontinuities after the rock mass model has been calibrated from results of endoscope logs. To carry out this task, Sandvik commissioned a Down-the Hole LDI550 drill rig equipped with a navigation system and an add-on to monitor more drilling parameters than the penetration rate that was started to be used from February 2023. Despite that this is a mature technology, it is worth noting that no such type of drill is used in any quarry in Spain, and from our knowledge it is also rare across Europe. The drilling parameters recorded in the CAN bus of the drill rig as function of time are:

- Rotation pressure: rotation motor pressure.
- Penetration rate: rate of penetration during drilling or moving feed system.
- Feed pressure.
- Compressor pressure : compressor air pressure
- Air flushing amount request: compressor air flow control request.
- Drilling bit depth measurement: current drill bit depth in hole.
- Drilling hole depth measurement: current (maximum) depth of the drilled hole. This will be updated and remain in maximum value where drilled depth has reached (regardless of bit has been pulled back). This value includes all drill pipes/rods added to steels.

Driller training and installation of the equipment to enable the drill rig navigation (noticeably a dedicated GPS base station and internet antenna) has been taking place since the commissioning of the drill rig. The importance of the navigation issue is not only that the drill records incorporate the borehole coordinates but that the drill needs this information to record MWD signals. For each blast, two types of files were obtained: (i) CEMEX retrieves from the drill rig with a memory stick, the IREDES quality file that provides among others the hole ID, coordinates of the collar, and starting drilling date and time, while (ii) SANDVIK downloads via WIFI the CANBUS file from which the three pressures, penetration rate and depth are obtained as function of time. UPM-M has written a MATLAB script to link both files and obtain for each hole the drilling data as function of depth. For this, the next operations are made on data in the CAN-BUS file: i) Finding groups of data with equal time value; ii) Computing mean value for all MWD properties; iii) filtering of missing data and zero depth values; iv) finding equal depth values for the same hole to calculate a unique representative value; v) sorting data in order according to date. The steps for the IREDES quality file are: i) filtering missing data and zero depth values; ii) finding equal depth values for the same hole to calculate a unique representative value; iii) data is already ordered by date and time, and it is combined with the records from CAN-BUS files.

In the three blasts (230503, 230518 and 230530) made in May 2023, the drilling plan for either single holes or several holes of the same row were manually entered by the operator, and the drill rig positioned manually over the marks of the hole's collars. In this process, the same holes IDs were used for most of the holes and the GPS signal was poor involving a low accuracy in the drill rig positioning and thus in the recorded coordinates. This makes that only 30 holes out of 65 could be aligned with the endoscope videos and used then to develop the MWD-based rock mass recognition model.

For the blasts made in June and July 2023 (230612, 230621, 230710 and 230714), the following process was carried out: 1) the drilling grid was marked in the block by the drill rig operator; 2) the coordinates of the marks were obtained from either 3D models based on UAV flights or a GPS TOPCOM HIPER SR; 3) these data was transferred to MAXAM's software to define the drilling plan that was then input to the drill rig through a memory stick. This working procedure leads to an acceptable error in the collar coordinates between actual and intended collar position for the first three blasts (up to 15 cm), while in blast 230714 there was a systematic bias of the collar towards the west of about 60 cm; the reasons for such deviations are still unknown. For these blasts, the MWD files for all the holes can be linked to the corresponding endoscope videos. Figure 5 shows the drill rig in blast 230612 and a snapshot of the alignment screen in which the planned position is given by the black circle and the current position by the green and blue circles. Problems were observed with the drilling rods during the testing period due to the rupture of three of them near the contact point between rods.

Currently, MWD data from 143 holes and the corresponding endoscope videos results are under analysis to develop a MWD-based model. Figure 6 shows three drilling parameters after processing raw signals (outlier removal, filtering the effect of rod addition, and removing the influence of the hole depth) for one of the holes; the signals are colored according to the lithologies recognized in the endoscope logs. Next actions are to reduce the classes of lithologies and discontinuities to three or four groups with different response and use machine learning techniques to build an MWD-based model that recognizes lithologies (e.g., different clay content) and discontinuities (e.g., cavities) that affect the drilling response, and that may have influence on the blasting outcome. The purpose is to use this model in the second blasting campaign to be made in 2024, to adapt the explosive properties to the rock mass characteristics.

Figure 5. Down-the Hole LDI550 drill rig (left) and alignment screen (right).

Figure 6. Processed MWD signals: feed pressure (top), rotation pressure (center), and penetration rate (bottom) with recognized lithologies in different colors: massive limestone without clay (yellow, 20), massive limestone with low amount of clay (green, 21) and massive limestone with medium clay content (blue, 22) in blasthole 4 in blast 230612 (bench 3, Northeast side of the quarry).

2.1.2 Adaptive blast design and novel explosives and blasting products and systems (Task 2.2.)

CEMEX carried out 15 blasts from January to July 2023 drilled with the burden and spacing between holes commonly used by the quarry. Their main characteristics are shown in Table 1. Summary of the characteristics of the blasts monitored in January-July 2023.. Nine baseline blasts were made with the current explosive and delay systems used in the quarry. Six additional blasts were charged with an on-site mixed watergel explosive sensitized using compressed air technology to allow selective energy delivery (see Figure 7). Electronic detonators were also used in these blasts.

Table 1. Summary of the characteristics of the blasts monitored in January-July 2023.

	Baseline	New techniques
Location	NE zone: Bench 3 (5 blasts) and Bench 2 (1 blast) N zone: Bench 1 (3 blasts)	NE zone: Bench 3 (3 blasts) N zone: Bench 1 (1 blast) and Bench 2 (2 blasts)
Explosive	ANFO (emulsion cartridges with water in the holes). Nominal mass obtained from CEMEX blasting logs.	RIOFLEX QY (cup density 0.64-1.25 g/cm ³ with mean and standard deviation 0.88 sd 0.10 g/cm ³) Actual mass provided by MAXAM: mass per hole, total produced, total dumped, etc.
Detonators	Non-electric	Electronic
Powder factor	0.33 sd 0.05 kg/m ³	0.40 sd. 0.07 kg/m ³ .

Figure 7. Mobile sensitizing unit used in blast 230530 (bench 1, North side) and charging of hole 27.

The pre-blast flight made for rock mass characterization made by UPM-M was also used to build a 3D model of the block and assess the geometry of the blast (i.e., current collar positions, burden, spacing, height, etc). UPM-M used a Pulsar Micro Probe Mk3 manufactured by Geo-Koncept to survey the actual path of the blastholes. The complicated layout of the blasts with the holes distributed in several rows makes necessary to prepare a MATLAB script that integrates the point cloud and the actual borehole path into a single model (see Figure 8). This enables to obtain the burden for each hole (see Figure 9)

Figure 8. Overview of blast 230710 with 31 holes in four rows (bench 2, North side of the pit); profiles of the holes of each rock are marked with a different color.

Figure 9. Burden distribution for each hole in blast 230710 obtained from the profiles in Figure 7.

The performance of the explosives was successfully measured in six out of eight blasts (see Table 2). Own manufactured carbon gauges and a power supply developed by UPM-M have been used to measure detonation pressure of ANFO and RIOFLEX QY.

Table 2. Explosive characterization measurements by UPM-M.

Blast	Explosive (Hole id)	Detonation P	VOD
230419	ANFO (H8)	Yes	No

230503	ANFO (H9)	Yes	Yes
230518	RIOFLEX QY (H10)	Yes	Yes
230530	RIOFLEX QY H12)	Yes	Yes
230612	RIOFLEX QY (H14)	Yes	Yes
230621	RIOFLEX QY H1)	Yes*	Yes
1230710	RIOFLEX QY (H1)	Yes*	Yes
1230714	RIOFLEX QY H1)	Yes	Yes

*The recording system do not work properly, and the signal could not be measured.

2.1.3 Blast output control: fragmentation, rock damage, muckpile properties and Innovative vibration measurement tools (Task 2.3.)

CEMEX installed in autumn 2022 a scale in belt C3 to monitor the mass of material below 90 mm that bypasses the primary crusher. The ratio of the mass of this material to the mass of the run-of-mine (ROM) feed into the plant (P90) is a significant fraction of the feed; it is in the range 91-29 % with mean and standard deviation (after sd.) of 46 sd 7 % for the 15-blast monitored, and accounts for both natural fines coming from the clay and small fragments produced by blasting.

Post-blast flights over the resulting muckpiles were conducted with the Matrix 300 RTK drone to assess the fragmentation of the material in the surface of the muckpile from the analysis of the resulting 3D models. The ROM from blast 230710 was partially mucked before the flight and the muckpile rearranged to allow working the backhoe excavator; hence, this blast will be likely discarded for the analysis. The primary crusher feed P90 values are expected to help in correcting the muckpile size distribution measured from the 3D photogrammetric models where errors from segregation of small particles beneath larger fragments and capturing errors encompass that the probability of a particle to appear on the surface of the muckpile diminishes as size decreases. This involves that fines tend to be missing on the surface and being more abundant in the unseen interior of the muckpile, which results in very steep size distributions.

The resulting muckpiles can be qualitatively classified depending on the pull and the area of the 3D model of the post-blast flight covered by fragmented rocks into two groups. Seven baseline blasts had a limited to medium pull, involving that a significant part of the block gets stuck (see the blue polygon in Figure 10-left), while blasts made with RIOFLEX and two baseline blasts (230131 and 230419) had more common muckpiles in which most of the material was thrown and fragmented (see Figure 10-right).

Figure 10. Post-blast models from blasts with limited to medium pull (left) and with medium to normal pull (right).

UPM-M used three bi-axial geophones (vertical and longitudinal) of range 2 m/s (see Table 2) and 12 x 34 mm in diameter and length, to monitor near field vibrations from five blasts made in spring 2023. The geophones were grouted with mortar to the bottom of a vertical borehole to achieve a stiff enough geophone-to-rock coupling. These measurements will be

used to build damage contours around boreholes. To validate the model, major damage or backbreak in the form of cracks apparent in the 3D post-blast models has been mapped with the JMX Analyst Module version 4.8). This has been made for six post-blast flights models with RTK enabled, which allows to integrate the blastholes into the post-blast model and quantify the extension of damage into the remaining rock mass (see Figure 11).

Figure 11. Damage analysis in blast 230503: point cloud of the muckpile after blasting (blue layer), last rows of blastholes (green and grey lines) and mapped cracks (red dots).

2.1.4 Drill-to-mill concept implementation (T2.4/WP6)

The influence of the blast downstream is evaluated with the data shown in Table 3. CEMEX delivers every month to UPM-M three Excel files with the main downstream parameters of the blasts. The dataset is completed with the information from the truck tracking system installed in the quarry by about. This system records the activities of the mobile machinery generally used to dig and haul the ROM, which are four dumpers of payload of 57 t, one small dumper of payload of 37 t and the two backhoe excavators. The backhoe operator assesses visually the quality of blasted material that, depending on the amount of clay and its humidity, is sent to the following locations (see Figure 12):

- Plant: good quality with low-medium clay amount (near red polygon, Figure 12).
- *Vertedero voladura* (landfill): bad quality material with high amount of clay (blue polygons, Figure 12).
- *Piedra en rama* stockpile: medium quality material with medium clay content, that cannot be processed in winter due its high humidity, and it is stocked in this pile until it dries; clay is separated naturally from the rock (orange polygon, Figure 12).
- *Acopio* (surge pile): storage pile of good quality material (red polygon, Figure 12).
- *Escollera* (armourstone) stockpile: large boulders, generally above 800 mm (green polygon, Figure 12).

Table 3. Description of downstream KPI database.

Name (ID)	Format/Provider	Content
Parte de carga (Log A)	Excel/CEMEX (email)	Gives the source of the material feed into the plant in a daily basis; it assumes that only material from one source is fed into the plant.
Producción camiones Valdilecha (Log B)	Excel/CEMEX (email)	Shows for a particular month, the number of trips made daily by each truck to the dumping points of the quarry. This includes also “rechazo vertedero” o “rechazo tradebe” (graded aggregate) or reject of the plant (material from belt C5) that has a bad quality and high content in clay and it is employed for the roads of the quarry, and it is sold to the waste dump of Tradebe to complete rehabilitation.
Truck tracking system (Log C)	Csv/Abaut (email)	Daily output of the truck and excavator tracking system; it allows to monitor and identify the loading and dumping points for each truck, as well as the time required for these activities. It also provides the loading time per truck spent by the excavator. It underestimates the number of trips made to the plant with respect to Log (B)
KPI Plant overall (Log D)	Excel/CEMEX (email)	Shows for a particular month, the main KPIs of the plant in a daily basis. KPIs from some days should be discarded as it comes from more than one source

Figure 12. Aerial view of the quarry with dumping and loading areas.

Figure 13 shows a flowsheet of the primary circuit of the plant. The material feed to the plant passes through a grizzly with a cut-off of 90 mm; the bypass (-90 mm) is sieved at 40 mm. The fraction smaller than 40 mm goes to a finger roller screen when it is dried and the amount of clay is low; the screen (abbreviated as CDD, Figure 13) cuts at 20 mm and the fraction smaller than 20 mm goes through belt C5 to the stock 0-40 mm, while the fraction 20-40 mm goes through belt scale C11 to the prestock. This screen that works mainly from April to October (dry season) recovers 8 % of the material. If the finger

roller screen is not working because the material is wet and/or has a high clay content, the material is conveyed to the stock through belt C5 (0-40 mm), which is considered the reject of the plant.

The material larger than 90 mm is crushed in a jaw crusher and the resulting material separated in a screen with two decks with cut sizes of 30 and 40 mm and conveyed by the belt C8 to the stockpile 0-30 mm. This fraction is nearly constant about 5 % of the mass fed into the plant.

Four weight scales monitor the mass flow of the final products obtained from each blast; these are the fractions: 0/30 (belt C8), 40/80 (belt C10), 0/40 (belt C5) and prestock or 20/40 (belt C11). The fraction 40/80 is produced under demand. The excel file with the plant parameters (log D, Table 3) provides for each day, the masses carried by these four belt scales (m_{ck}) and by the bypass belt C3 (m_{C3}). It also stores the working hours of the plant (t_{oper}); the idle time (t_{down}) in which the primary part of the plant is not working when it was scheduled to work, the mass of ROM processed ($m_{plant} = m_{C8} + m_{C10} + m_{C5} + m_{C11}$), the working time of the finger roller screen (t_{CDD}), and the energy consumption of the equipment in the primary W_{plant} (i.e. crusher, feeder, belts, primary screens, etc).

Figure 13. Flowsheet of the primary circuit of the processing plant

The information from the truck tracking system (Log C, Table 3) is used to filter out the days from the plant performance file (log D, Table 3), when more than 5 % of the mass fed into the plant comes from other sources different than the muckpile of the blast under study. This allows us to investigate the effect of blast design downstream, discarding the bias produced in the plant by other materials that do not come from the blast. Figure 14 shows as an example that the material fed to the plant on May 26th, 2023, comes from the blast 230518 (red circles) also from the *Acopio* stockpile (black circles). Hence, the corresponding plant data for that day is discarded. The data obtained from Log D is used to calculate the performance parameters in Table 4.

Figure 14. Loading sources of the material fed into the plant on May 26th 2023 obtained from the truck tracking system.

Table 4 Calculated parameters that describe the plant performance.

Parameter (unit)	Formula
Fraction of material fed to the plant <90 mm, P90	m_{C3} / m_{plant}
Fraction of final products*, F_{Ck} (%)	m_{Ck} / m_{plant}
Normalized working time of the plant, t_{plant} (%)	$t_{oper} / (t_{oper} + t_{down})$
Working time of CDD per unit mass of fraction <90 mm, T_{CDD} (h/t)	t_{CDD} / m_{C3}
Electrical consumption of the equipment in the primary circuit normalized by the mass fed into the plant, w_{plant} (kWh/t)	W_{plant} / m_{plant}

* F_{C11} is the prestock and F_{C5} the plant reject

The purpose of blasting will be to reduce the fines produced by the blast, decreasing then the mass of material that bypasses the crusher (i.e. P_{90}) for an equal amount of natural fines, increasing the prestock (fraction F_{C11}), decreasing the reject (F_{C5}), and increasing the normalized working time of the plant. The working time of CDD will show the quality of the material, being low when clay is abundant or when low fines are produced by blasting.

2.1.5 Productive and energy efficient drilling of hard rocks (Task 2.5.)

Sandvik has facilitated the Valdilecha quarry with a Leopard D1550 Down-The-Hole drilling rig (Figure 15).

Figure 15 Sandvik D1550 drill rig at Valdilecha quarry.

The rig is capable of producing high-quality blast holes with minimal deviation. The rig is mounted with the TIM3D drill navigation system. The system relies on satellite-based navigation to accurately determine both the initial drilling position and the precise trajectory in strict adherence to the predefined drilling plan. The implementation of the TIM3D navigation system leads to enhancements in blast hole quality and precision of blast hole placement. Consequently, this contributes to improved rock fragmentation and ultimately improved operational efficiency in downstream processes of hauling, loading and comminution. Additionally, the system eliminates the necessity for conventional survey practices and any marking requirements, mitigating the potential for marking inaccuracies and significantly expediting the drilling process. The coordinate data from the TIM3D system can be exported from the rig as an IREDES quality report (Figure 16).

In addition to hole production, the drilling rig also provides measurement while drilling (MWD) data which can and is being utilized for rock mass characterization. Sandvik's Valdilecha rig is mounted with a logger that records data from the CAN bus. The captured drilling parameters are feed pressure, rotation pressure, air flushing request, drill bit depth, drill hole depth, rotation head speed, rotation head position, drilling state, and compressor pressure. Additionally, drilling penetration rate is calculated with TIM3D system and can be exported from the rig as IREDES MWD report (figure y). Some of the parameters mentioned above are used for the rock mass characterization model. A more detailed description of the data transfer from the rig and the data handling of the raw data is described in the chapter 2.1.1.2.

Select time period Start: 01-01-2023 End: 29-11-2023

Run report

Production summary Daily production report

1/1/2023 - 11/29/2023

Drill rig	Drilled accepted meters (m)	Engine hours (hh:mm)	Drilling time (hh:mm)	Number of accepted holes (pcs)	Average drilling utilization (%)	Avg length of accepted holes (m)	Avg drilling time per accepted hole (min)	Avg penetration speed (accepted meters)	Drilled accepted meters / engine hour (m/h)	Total fuel used (l)	Avg fuel consumption per hour (l/h)	Avg fuel consumption per accepted meter (l/m)	Avg fuel consumption per accepted hole (l/pcs)
Total	0	2:18	0:00	0	0	0.0	0.0	0.00	0.0	35	15.2	0.00	0.0
6/17/2023													
79032	58	2:06	0:46	3	35.5	19.3	15.3	1.26	27.6	87	41.4	1.50	29.0
Total	58	2:06	0:46	3	35.5	19.3	15.3	1.26	27.6	87	41.4	1.50	29.0
6/16/2023													
79032	198	7:18	2:37	11	35.8	18.0	14.3	1.26	27.1	268	40.8	1.51	27.1
Total	198	7:18	2:37	11	35.8	18.0	14.3	1.26	27.1	268	40.8	1.51	27.1
6/15/2023													
79032	58	2:24	0:51	3	35.4	19.3	17.0	1.14	24.2	52	21.7	0.90	17.3
Total	58	2:24	0:51	3	35.4	19.3	17.0	1.14	24.2	52	21.7	0.90	17.3
6/14/2023													
79032	41	2:09	0:40	3	31.0	13.7	13.3	1.02	19.1	89	41.4	2.17	29.7
Total	41	2:09	0:40	3	31	13.7	13.3	1.02	19.1	89	41.4	2.17	29.7
6/13/2023													
79032	194	6:39	2:45	10	41.4	19.4	16.5	1.18	29.2	286	43.0	1.47	28.6
Total	194	6:39	2:45	10	41.4	19.4	16.5	1.18	29.2	286	43.0	1.47	28.6
6/12/2023													
79032	0	1:27	0:28	0	32.2	0.0	0.0	0.00	0.0	50	34.5	0.00	0.0
Total	0	1:27	0:28	0	32.2	0.0	0.0	0.00	0.0	50	34.5	0.00	0.0
6/9/2023													
79032	0	0:45	0:00	0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.00	0.0	0	0.0	0.00	0.0
Total	0	0:45	0:00	0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.00	0.0	0	0.0	0.00	0.0

Figure 18. Showing a capture of daily production report from DI550 rig in Cemex Valdilecha quarry.

Figure 19. Shows the utilization % of the hours the rig has been available on 1.1.2023 - 29.11.2023.

2.2 Identification of data inputs from cyber & physical quarrying system and development of sensors, automation and process control (WP3)

2.2.1 Monitoring sensors and analysing tools for Mobile Machinery (Task 3.3.)

The activities carried out in Cemex by about are related to the monitoring and reporting of the fleet activities. The monitoring tool based on about's technology have 2 components:

- Hardware: The hardware installed in the cabin collects and transmit all the information regarding the physical activities of the machines. The plug-and-play sensor system can be installed in any machine from any manufacturer. The system just needs to have a 12/24V connector to operate not having the need to be connected to any electronic device or computer of the machine. In addition, the system has an antenna able to transmit the information collected by the sensor to about's platform. For more information about architecture and installation, please check D3.6 - Chapter 3.

- Software: The software of about analyses and reports the different information coming from the sensors for being reported as fleet KPIs. The software access and monitoring are self-managed by the users (e.g., user rights and access, creation of working areas, etc) and report the different fleet KPIs fleets to the AI-ML algorithm developed by about. For detailed information please refer to D3.5 - Chapters 5.1 & 6.1. All the information provided by about’s expert system can be sorted and filtered according to time, location [according to its name or mine location], machinery, activity or KPI of interest. The tool offers a full filtering option for displaying the KPIs needed quickly and in an understandable way. The same information reported in the files mentioned above in D3.5 - Chapter 4.1.1 is displayed in about’s expert system.

2.3 Development of an integrated IoT/BIM/AI platform for smart quarrying (WP4)

2.3.1 ICT platform design and implementation (Task 4.2)

As described in the public deliverable D4.2 “Report on IQS design and architecture”, an Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS) has been designed and implemented by Akkodis. This ICT solution enables the quarry, according to its specific expert systems and partners involved in its business processes (as presented in the section 3 “Data flows between the expert systems of the quarries and the IQS” of the D4.2) to collect, store, transform and share relevant data that could be used for any actionable insights. The main blocks of the IQS are:

- All the components of the Data Lake (refer to the section 4.1.1 of the D4.2).
- The interface tools such as the CDMP, the shared data builder, generic and specific proxies (connectors) and REST APIs (refer to the section 4.1.2 of the D4.2).
- All the components of the IoT platform (refer to the section 4.2 of the D4.2).
- The reporting and management tools (refer to the section 4.3 of the D4.2).

2.3.2 Data warehouse-AI (Task 4.3.)

This task included:

- The design of the Data Warehouse that is part of the IQS (Intelligent Quarry System) that has as main objective to provide a data processing framework for quarry processes.

The Data Warehouse is designed in the framework of the IQS global system that seats in the cloud. It is not specifically designed for this pilot. Nevertheless, it encompasses the functionality of storing and processing data specifically for CEMEX-Valdilecha also.

- The design of specific AI services which are summarised in the following table:

Table 5: AI Services developed for the different pilots.

AI Service Area	Pilot site	SIGMA	UPM-AI
Hawkeye (CV) COLORIMETRY (QUAL)	CEMEX	X	X
Hawkeye (CV) GRAIN SIZE	CEMEX	X	X
Stock Forecast (CV) STOCKPILE VOLUME	Holcim & Vicat	X	X
Predictive Maintenance (PrMa) - ANOMALIES DETECTION (Acoustic&video&...)	CSI	X	X

Metaquarry (Document Mgt)	Holcim & Vicat	X	
Consumptions & production forecast	CIMPOR	X	X

It is important to mention that there are two deliverables that describe the two development areas and that can be used as a more detailed reference:

- D4.3 Report on the AI Algorithms and Services.
- D4.4 Report on the Architecture of the Data Warehouse and its Integration.

The first service aims at estimating the composition of aggregates inline production using visual inputs captured by cameras. This service is being implemented in CEMEX-Valdilecha in which limestones are being extracted as aggregates. Together with this material, clays appear, which represent non-profitable waste, and which is desired to minimize or, at least, differentiate to optimize the processes in the treatment plant.

In addition, one of the key factors in classifying the final product of aggregates is the size of the particles that make up the material, as the size of the particles in aggregates plays a crucial role in determining their suitability for different applications. In this regard, the aim of the second AI service implemented in CEMEX-Valdilecha is to automate the process of determining whether the treated material meets technical specifications. By analyzing the screening efficiency, it can quickly identify any issues with the screening process. This allows for timely repairs or replacements of screens, ensuring the proper functioning of material treatment processes.

Therefore, in the case of the CEMEX-Valdilecha Pilot, two AI services have been designed specifically. The two services are centered on the analysis of the quality of the material. Firstly, in the primary section of the plant that is analysing images from 2 cameras installed at the primary crusher and at a conveyor belt which is used to carry the material that is rejected at the roller screen of the latter crusher. In this way all the material that enters the plant is supervised by Computer Vision algorithms that **process the colour of the material** and determines if the material being processed is of the expected quality or adjustments have to be made in the extraction and material selection processes, before entering the plant.

Secondly, at the secondary section of the plant, another camera has been installed at a conveyor belt that is used to transport the produced 4-20 mm material to its stockpile from the specific material silo. In this case a **granulometry service** is supervising that the size of the aggregates produced is what is expected.

2.3.2.1 Data Warehouse Development

When digitising data for an industrial application what is important is to conceive a flexible data storage facility, the Datalake in the IQS, and other means to gather only relevant data that is key for answering business questions. This last entity is the Data Warehouse (DWH). The requirements that were followed to come up with a practical solution were the following:

- **The DWH must make information easily accessible:** the information contained in the DWH must be understandable and intuitive, not only for the developer but also for the business user, reflecting the vocabulary of the business.
- **The DWH must present information consistently:** data in the DWH must share common labels and definitions across data sources, what implies that, if two measurements have the same name, they must mean the same thing.
- **The DWH must adapt to change:** the DWH must be able to handle changes in user needs, business conditions, etc., in an easy way, not invalidating existing data.
- **The DWH must present information in a timely way:** raw data must be converted into actionable information as soon as possible.
- **The DWH must protect its information assets:** the DWH must put in place the necessary measures to ensure that only authorized users can access its data.

- **The DWH must serve as the foundation for improved decision making:** the data stored in the DWH must serve to support business decisions.
- **The business community must accept the DWH:** the business community must embrace and actively use the DWH, so it must contain actionable information and be simple and fast.
- **The DWH must support the KPIs defined in the project:** the ultimate goal of the DWH is to allow the measurement of the project KPIs. Thus, the DWH must be able to acquire the necessary information to calculate them and to store them with the appropriate structure.
- **The DWH must be able to access data from the Data Lake through the CDMP component:** the DWH obtains the data it requires from the Data Lake. For this reason, it must be able to interface with this component, adapting to its interfaces and authentication methods.
- **The DWH must be able to interface with PowerBI:** the PowerBI tool has been selected to serve as the dashboard for the IQS. Thus, the DWH must be able to integrate with this tool, providing it with access to the stored data.
- **The DWH must be able to access information contained in documents and through SQL:** the DWH must be able to process the file formats used to store information in the Data Lake (namely .csv and .xls).
- **The DWH must provide a secure API:** an application interface, such as REST API, is required to make the DWH data available to external services, such as the Forecast AI service, without the need for PowerBI. This API must be secured through a standard method (e.g., OAuth2.0).

The DWH must connect to the Datalake easily and the PowerBI tool that is being used to generate the Dashboards showing the most relevant KPIs from the different pilots including Cemex-Valdilecha. Additionally, it can be connected to external sources such as **The Portuguese Institute for Sea and Atmosphere (IPMA)**. The Architecture diagram is shown below:

Figure 20. DWH Architecture.

As it was decided after a benchmark on DWH solutions, as reported on deliverable D4.1 (DigiEcoQuarry Consortium, 2022), Google’s BigQuery was selected due to its better pricing and documentation, compared to its alternatives.

Thus, the BigQuery component is in charge of the actual data storage. BigQuery is a fully managed and serverless data warehouse that includes analysis capabilities over big amounts of data. Interactions with this component, such as data insertion or extraction, are done through an SQL dialect. BigQuery also imposes that all requests are authenticated, supporting different mechanisms, such as OAuth2.0 1.

The BigQuery instance that is used in DigiEcoQuarry is configured in such a way that data from a certain quarry can only be accessed by those with permissions to that data. This is achieved with the creation of five Data Warehouses, one for each quarry, and thus one is available for CEMEX data.

1 <https://cloud.google.com/bigquery>

Data in BigQuery is organized in **tables** as shown in the following table:

Table 6: Example of table created in BigQuery.

	TempoODate	IdBatch	Passante2Num1	Passante2Num1	Passante2Num1	SogliaVuotoPes	Passante2Num5	Assorbimento9%
▶ cimpor ☆	45127.4307...	35	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0
csi ☆	45132.4759...	35	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0
▶ hanson ☆	45132.4759...	35	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0
▼ holcim ☆	45131.2883...	35	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	44.3
TotalProduction ☆	45133.7536...	35	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	39.0
calendar ☆	45133.7536...	35	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	39.0
maestro ☆	45133.7536...	35	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	39.0
maestro_data ☆	45133.7536...	35	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	39.0
▶ roccosa ☆	45133.7536...	35	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	39.0
▼ vicat ☆	45133.7536...	35	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	39.0
allocationMatrixModule ☆	45133.7536...	35	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	39.0
consumable ☆	45133.7536...	35	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	39.0
module ☆	45133.7536...	35	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	39.0

As stated above, further detailed information about the DWH can be found in the deliverable D4.4.

2.3.2.2 Artificial Intelligence Services Development

2.3.2.2.1 Quality Determination Service (colorimetry)

This service aims at estimating the quality of aggregates (composition) in line production using visual inputs captured by cameras. The system will be non-intrusive and will allow for maximizing the run of the mining process by improving site planning and controlling the grinding process. It will also support automated notifications and keep a historical record to further analyze the data. The information will be collected and processed while keeping the mine in production, fostering direct actions on the operations.

In this regard, it would be desirable to develop a technology for automatic material classification that would enable monitoring rock type continuously at any stage of the mine operation to distinguish between the target and waste materials.

For the CEMEX-Valdilecha pilot, a new non-invasive and high-resolution technology applied to the classification of the material in aggregate quarries using colorimetry together with the textural characteristics of the materials of interest after considering their chemical characterization as well as the spectral analysis is required. Therefore, a system composed of two cameras was conceived after analysing different alternatives for the positioning. The aim is to get images from all the material that is entering the plant (ground truth). The positions can be seen in the following picture and diagram of the plant:

Figure 21. Cameras positioning at the Valdilecha Primary (Positions marked 1 and 2).

The proposed process architecture (applying Computer Vision processes) for the service taking into consideration the two cameras is the following:

Figure 22. Flowchart of the proposed processes of quality determination service.

Preliminary studies were carried out on limestone and clay samples were taken from the Valdilecha quarry site in order to be analysed at the UPM laboratories.

Below a picture of the prepared samples for laboratory analysis is shown:

Figure 23. Detail of the prepared samples analyzed to determine the aggregate quality by colorimetry.

A: limestones, B: muds, C: mixture of powdered limestones and muds.

The following processes were applied to the material:

- a) X-ray diffraction (XRD)
- b) Spectrophotometry

Detailed results can be seen in deliverable D4.3.

The Architecture components that are being used to process the data generated by the service is presented below:

Figure 24. General Architecture diagram for the CV AI services.

The main characteristics of the solution are the following:

1. **Communication:** Data will be sent from the quarry using 3-4G networking (a modem and a SIM are integrated on the local PC) throughput provided by the Movistar Spanish IOT network.
2. **CV Models:** To build a robust and accurate computer vision model is needed data collection, preparation, and annotation, model training and evaluation. Therefore, this pipeline involves a lot of data and that is why a first processing step will be performed locally to obtain a dataset, send images to Sigma cloud and train a model. Most of the CV algorithms/models and image processing will be developed and improved in Sigma cloud and once they are validated, they are deployed in the local PC at the quarry. Here it is important to highlight the cloud CV Computation model is used to perform continuous model improvement based on the data (Images) that are taken by the local components.
3. **Image acquisition and processing:** it involves preprocessing, processing and decision making with a computer that will be used to control the cameras (acquisition) and process the images that are captured. The best model will be always used and stored at the image processing block locally in such a way that the results are computed in real time and in order to avoid high communication costs and unwanted delays if implemented remotely. The decision model block will make the needed calculations based on the Mathematical model to allow the evaluation of the Models. The results will be compared with the ground truth (images annotated by hand) and decide if further model improvement is needed. If not, the results are stored.
4. **Storage:** Only results and relevant data will be stored in the IQS (Datalake and Datawarehouse) after processing has been done in the cloud. So, for example, images/videos will not be sent regularly to the Datalake, Raw processing data will be also excluded. Only sampled results per day will be sent.
5. **Data processing:** In the Data Warehouse the information will be organized in several tables for each one of the two services: Material Quality and Granulometry.
6. **Data filtering:** Queries will be programmed within the Data Warehouse in order to optimize the dashboard processing in PowerBi.
7. **Results:** The results of the AI algorithms will be displayed for these services on the CEMEX/Valdilecha Dashboard. In D4.4 the dashboard organization is explained.

As for the CV methodologies analyzed, two methodologies/technologies were tested for the two cameras:

- a) Non-supervised segmentation based on K-means.

Figure 25. Results of the K-means algorithm on images with different lightings.

This approach works properly in a fully controlled environment, but it is very sensitive to any variation in the image, for example lighting changes.

- b) Supervised deep learning-based segmentation using CNNs.

To implement this segmentation method the following steps are needed:

- 1) Data collection, preparation, and annotation.
- 2) Model training and evaluation.

CNNs is a supervised type of deep learning that requires data and corresponding annotated labels to train a model.

In order to train the latter, it is necessary to collect a dataset containing images of the material. Initially the images were taken with a phone since there was no camera installed in the facility. And data annotators labelled the corresponding images, following guidelines that were specifically edited to classify the material into 4 categories depending on the clay observed over the limestone.

An example on how the images are processed is displayed below.

Figure 26. Example of an original image (left) and the result after using the segmentation model that was trained with labelled data.

For the C3 conveyor belt the two approaches (CV model and algorithms: Kmeans and supervised CNN) were also tested. Images of the results are appended below:

Figure 27. Results of clay segmentation based on K-means on images captured at the quarry.

Figure 28. Result of the analysis using annotated images taken at the lab, with mixed fragments of limestone and clays.

- Physical installation

During the month of October 2023, the equipment was installed at the Cemex-Valdilecha quarry pilot as can be seen in the following figure, where most of the elements of the solution are represented (Camera, industrial controlling PC, antenna, screen, power supply...)

Figure 29. Installed equipment photos.

2.3.2.2.2 Granulometry Service

The size of the particles in aggregates plays a crucial role in determining their suitability for different applications. Aggregates are often classified into different size ranges, such as coarse aggregates, fine aggregates, or graded aggregates, based on the size of the grains. These size classifications help determine the appropriate use of the aggregates in various construction and engineering applications. The material after being crushed is screened and separated into different sizes.

One of the product lines, sizes between 4 and 20mm, is being verified with the Computer Vision approach that was designed. The aim of this AI service is to automate the process of determining whether the treated material meets technical specifications. By analyzing the screening efficiency, it can quickly identify any issues with the screening process. This allows for timely repairs or replacements of screens, ensuring the proper functioning of material treatment processes.

The camera system was installed at the secondary section of the plant as shown in the following pictures (see the yellow and orange rectangles):

Figure 30. Camera installed at the conveyor belt C33 of the secondary at Valdilecha.

The component architecture is exactly the same as for the service above (See Fig.5). An electrical connection diagram is shown that contains the physical elements used /Camera, lights, power supply and the industrial PC used that embeds a Communication PCI.

Figure 31. Granulometry Service HW components interconnection.

The computer vision processed that were used to develop the solution is depicted below.

Figure 32: A flowchart of the proposed processes of grain size determination service.

Two model approaches that were tested were the following:

1) Edge detector based on DexiNed-Based Neural Network

The 2 steps followed to construct the solution based on this model were:

1. *Image preprocessing*: the raw input images are preprocessed with gray scaling to reduce complexity by keeping only one channel of the image and contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) to have higher contrast and sharper edges.
2. *Edge detection, contour segmentation and filtering*: the grayscale image is fed into the DexiNed network to extract the edges of the image.

Material samples were taken on a very similar abandoned quarry having the same material composition very near Valdilecha. The tests were performed at a laboratory premises. To show how the model works, the results obtained from an image taken at the above quarry, a sequence of processed images is attached.

Figure 33. Image processed in different steps based on the Dexined neural network.

2) Supervised deep learning-based segmentation

The second approach that was tested to solve this service was based on deep learning-based techniques. The reason to consider this type of approach for this service is that using the data agnostic model, the final segmentation not only captures those rocks that lay on the top layer of the conveyor belt, but also those in lower layers.

Just as for the colorimetry service, an annotation process had to be performed at SIGMA premises using the related samples. In fact, three different datasets were generated: training, validation, and test datasets.

The results obtained with this approach using images taken at the lab and from the conveyor belt in Valdilecha are displayed below.

Photographs taken at the lab

Photographs taken at the quarry

Figure 34. Segmentation results obtained with the Deep Learning approach.

- Physical Installation of the CV system

Figure 35. Pictures of the camera, antenna and power supply installed at the Valdilecha's secondary.

The system comprised basically the same elements as for the colorimetry/quality service. Communication to the cloud to send images is implemented using an IOT 4G network.

After getting the first images, camera parameters were fine tuned to increase the quality of the photos. Some shots are appended below.

Figure 36. Captured images by the C4/20 conveyor belt camera at the Valdilecha's secondary.

2.3.3 BIM integration (Task 4.4.)

The project's foundation for Task 4.4 rested on the integration of innovative Building Information Modelling (BIM) methodologies. BIM, as defined by the US National Building Information Model Standard Project Committee and the ISO 19650-1:2018, represents a digital manifestation of the physical and functional attributes of a facility. It serves as a shared knowledge resource, forming a reliable basis for informed decision-making throughout a facility's life cycle, from conception to demolition.

In the broader context of architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC), BIM has evolved into a transformative process that transcends traditional representations of building components. By generating and managing digital representations of physical and functional characteristics, BIM offers a spectrum of benefits, including enhanced collaboration, visualization, accurate cost estimation, and comprehensive data for efficient facility management. Recognizing the versatility of BIM across various industries, Valdilecha embraced the potential for efficient project management, collaboration, and sustainability within the mining and quarry sector. The following points present the activities carried out to achieve the established goals within T4.4.

2.3.3.1 BIM Models

In the initial phase of the project, the focus was on ensuring the availability of a 3D model for the quarry, which served as the foundational element for subsequent conversion to Industry Foundation Classes (IFC), seamlessly integrating it into the overarching project framework. For the Valdilecha quarry, the treatment plant's 3D model was developed based on drone flight images, CAD files, general quarry photos, and the graphic process scheme. The model encapsulates the general geometry of all visible treatment plant assets, including conveyor belts. In collaboration with the pilot site team, a list of mobile machinery in use was incorporated into the model. Developed in Autodesk Revit, the model seamlessly integrates treatment plant assets, mobile machinery, and the latest topographical data from drone flights conducted under "WP1: Towards the Digital Innovative Quarry." This comprehensive digital representation not only facilitates current project needs but also lays the groundwork for future BIM strategies and data-driven decision-making processes. Further details and insights can be explored in "Deliverable D4.5. BIM Planning for all the Pilots."

Figure 37. Valdilecha Treatment Plant and Mobile Machinery 3D Model.

2.3.3.2 4D BIM Planning & Time-Location Planning

The integration of 3D models with project schedules, known as 4D BIM Planning, has revolutionized construction and project management. In the mining and quarrying sector, the DEQ framework aimed to validate the applicability of 4D BIM Planning across pilot sites.

At CEMEX Valdilecha, the challenge was to streamline project schedules without detailed plans. Schedules were crafted using diverse sources, including open data and Valdilecha pilot site insights. An advanced planning software with a robust BIM module was used for centralized schedules, tailored to Valdilecha's needs. Activities tracking and 4D visualization tools enhanced operational efficiency.

Accurate IFC models in the right coordinate system were crucial for seamless integration. The linking process required distinct assets in 3D models, ensuring precise association with Valdilecha's schedule. Correct data structures ensured consistency during linking. Treating mobile machinery as resources, not 3D elements, enhanced 4D scheduling efficiency.

The 4D BIM Plan at Valdilecha visualized quarry operations, monitored equipment and resource allocation, and tracked project progress. Long-term planning covered the entire quarry lifecycle, incorporating retrospective scheduling, volumetric models, and mobile machinery allocation. A 4D BIM Simulation integrated models, work program data, and progress tracking. Resource allocation and mass haulage studies optimized machinery usage, producing cut-and-fill diagrams for efficient material transportation.

4D BIM Planning, with advanced tools, benefits the Valdilecha quarry, addressing unique challenges in mining and quarrying. Detailed analyses and simulations at Valdilecha demonstrate practical applications, offering insights for improved operational efficiency, resource allocation, and sustainable mining practices. More details are available in "Deliverable D4.5. BIM Planning for all the Pilots."

Figure 38. Valdilecha: 4D BIM Simulation Flipbook Summary

2.3.3.3 Common Data Environment (CDE)

Valdilecha's journey towards a Model-based Common Data Environment (CDE) commenced with the upload of IFC models to Autodesk Tandem. This strategic move facilitated the creation of a live Digital Twin, seamlessly integrating real-time data from WP3 partners. The CDE became a dynamic platform for Valdilecha's management team, offering detailed visualizations of quarry processes and performance.

By linking 3D models with real-time data, Valdilecha's team gained a holistic understanding of each element's behaviour over time. Customized dashboards streamlined monitoring and decision-making, optimizing operational strategies and enhancing overall performance.

As a cautionary note, Valdilecha's team was encouraged to recognize that while the information showcased valuable insights, it should be approached with caution in real-world operational contexts until data flow from third parties to the DataLake was fluent and verified. For those interested in delving deeper, detailed information is available in "Deliverable D4.5. BIM Planning for all the Pilots."

Figure 39. CDE as a Digital Twin. Connection with external data.

3 Conclusions

Valdilecha pilot site's activities up to this point to this point have mainly consisted in supporting and implementing technologies, solutions, and research in collaborations with the other partners of the project. As pilot site it has been fundamental to share our know-how and a deep understanding of the processes, thus communicating the needs from productive and operative point of view and identifying where there is a margin for improvement and the directions for enhancing the KPIs the technologies develop have been successfully implemented, we carried out the assessment and monitoring of relevant KPIs and performed impact assessment for the entire value chine using Standardises KPI's

As a pilot site, it has been essential to share our knowledge of the processes, thus communicating the needs from a production and operational point of view and identifying where there is room for improvement and the directions to take in order to improve the KPIs. The first fundamental step in improving production performance (improving the KPIs) is to acquire sufficient data to better monitor the processes, thus also having enough information to calculate the KPIs and estimate the evolution of performance. Scales, sensors, and cameras have been installed, and in future the data will be sent automatically to the system so that it will be possible to study process performance in detail.

In the next months it is expected to go through some important steps such as:

- Training of the driller to validate the methodology developed by Sandvik and to increase the database covering lithologies with higher clay content than previous blasters.
- Converge the data provided by Abaut and data monitored by the quarry.
- Define relevant KPI's for the quarry process optimization.
- Second blasting campaign planification.

The upcoming solutions are very promising, and we are looking forward to developing them. We get a wider view of the project.

4 References

D3.5 Machinery in Loading and Internal/External report on expert system design and architecture.

D1.1 Requirements for improved extraction, rock mass characterisation and control report.

List of Figures

Figure 1. Images of the antennas system installed: left – WIFI receptor, centre – master antenna, right – mobile antenna.	8
Figure 2. 3D model of blast 230612 and mapped discontinuities (green and red horizontal axes define the North and East directions).	9
Figure 3. Block model of bench 3 in the Northeast part of the pit; the colors correspond to different lithologies: massive limestone with no clay (blue); massive limestone with low amount of clay (magenta); massive limestone with medium amount of clay (red); brecciated limestone with low amount of clay (green); brecciated limestone with medium amount of clay (yellow), brecciated limestone with high amount of clay (grey) and clay (brown).	10
Figure 4. SVM confusion matrix for lithology classification from footage extracted from endoscope videos.	11
Figure 5. Down-the Hole LDI550 drill rig (left) and alignment screen (right).	12
Figure 6. Processed MWD signals: feed pressure (top), rotation pressure (center), and penetration rate (bottom) with recognized lithologies in different colors: massive limestone without clay (yellow, 20), massive limestone with low amount of clay (green, 21) and massive limestone with medium clay content (blue, 22) in blasthole 4 in blast 230612 (bench 3, Northeast side of the quarry).	13
Figure 7. Mobile sensitizing unit used in blast 230530 (bench 1, North side) and charging of hole 27.	14
Figure 8. Overview of blast 230710 with 31 holes in four rows (bench 2, North side of the pit); profiles of the holes of each rock are marked with a different color.	15
Figure 9. Burden distribution for each hole in blast 230710 obtained from the profiles in Figure 7.	15
Figure 10. Post-blast models from blasts with limited to medium pull (left) and with medium to normal pull (right).	16
Figure 11. Damage analysis in blast 230503: point cloud of the muckpile after blasting (blue layer), last rows of blastholes (green and grey lines) and mapped cracks (red dots).	17
Figure 12. Aerial view of the quarry with dumping and loading areas.	18
Figure 13. Flowsheet of the primary circuit of the processing plant.	19
Figure 14. Loading sources of the material fed into the plant on May 26 th 2023 obtained from the truck tracking system.	20
Figure 15 Sandvik DI550 drill rig at Valdilecha quarry.	21
Figure 16. Showing the IREDES MWD (left) and quality report (right).	22
Figure 17. Showing the SanRemo production report summary of DI550 rig in Cemex Valdilecha quarry 1.1.2023 - 29.11.2023.	22
Figure 18. Showing a capture of daily production report from DI550 rig in Cemex Valdilecha quarry.	23
Figure 19. Shows the utilization % of the hours the rig has been available on 1.1.2023 - 29.11.2023.	23
Figure 20. DWH Architecture.	26
Figure 21. Cameras positioning at the Valdilecha Primary (Positions marked 1 and 2).	28
Figure 22. Flowchart of the proposed processes of quality determination service.	29
Figure 23. Detail of the prepared samples analyzed to determine the aggregate quality by colorimetry.	29
Figure 24. General Architecture diagram for the CV AI services.	30
Figure 25. Results of the K-means algorithm on images with different lightings.	31

Figure 26. Example of an original image (left) and the result after using the segmentation model that was trained with labelled data..... 31

Figure 27. Results of clay segmentation based on K-means on images captured at the quarry. 32

Figure 28. Result of the analysis using annotated images taken at the lab, with mixed fragments of limestone and clays. 32

Figure 29. Installed equipment photos. 33

Figure 30. Camera installed at the conveyor belt C33 of the secondary at Valdilecha..... 34

Figure 31. Granulometry Service HW components interconnection..... 34

Figure 32: A flowchart of the proposed processes of grain size determination service..... 34

Figure 33. Image processed in different steps based on the Dexined neural network..... 35

Figure 34. Segmentation results obtained with the Deep Learning approach..... 36

Figure 35. Pictures of the camera, antenna and power supply installed at the Valdilecha’ s secondary..... 36

Figure 36. Captured images by the C4/20 conveyor belt camera at the Valdilecha’ s secondary..... 37

Figure 37. Valdilecha Treatment Plant and Mobile Machinery 3D Model. 38

Figure 38. Valdilecha: 4D BIM Simulation Flipbook Summary 39

Figure 39. CDE as a Digital Twin. Connection with external data. 40

List of Tables

Table 1. Summary of the characteristics of the blasts monitored in January-July 2023.....	13
Table 2. Explosive characterization measurements by UPM-M.	15
Table 3. Description of downstream KPI database.....	18
Table 4 Calculated parameters that describe the plant performance.....	20
Table 5: AI Services developed for the different pilots.	24
Table 6: Example of table created in BigQuery.....	27